

THE ROLE OF TEACHING THE PYTHON PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE IN COMPUTER SCIENCE FOR SCHOOLCHILDREN.

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Informatics is currently the most changing in the field of educational content discipline, both among school disciplines and among subjects studied in universities and educational institutions of secondary vocational education. It should be noted that in at the moment, Pascal or Basic are being studied as programming languages, in connection with which there is a logical question is whether there is a need for future teachers to learn the Python language computer science students at the university, is there a need for seniors to master the basics of this language schoolchildren. Of course, the study of Python by schoolchildren, as the first programming language, can cause some legitimate concerns: these will include, first of all, dynamic typing and high-level language. For example, replacing the concept of "array" with a high-level list does not gives schoolchildren a full opportunity to analyze the principles of the internal organization of the array. However, the advantages of learning Python as the first programming language in school. Python programs are much more concise than Pascal, which greatly simplifies the task of getting to know each other. with the language for novice programmers, since finding errors and debugging requires significantly less time costs. Python is a high-level programming language that makes it easy to learn how to write code. It also ranks among the top ten programming languages. Learning the basics of coding becomes easier with Python for both kids and beginners, as most Python commands are just plain English words. Beginners don't need to juggle binary representations to learn how to program in Python. There are several tools for writing code with a simple and intuitive interface. They encourage children to try their hand at programming, thereby satisfying their need to learn Python. Reasons why kids should learn Python: Python is one of the most flexible programming languages. It has an easy to read command set and a syntax that is much less complex than other programming languages. These commands are just plain English words, making learning Python more accessible for kids. Kids don't need to read a lot of textbooks to get started coding in Python. Learning Python for kids is doable, even if they don't have any prior knowledge of programming. Python has an

extensive standard library that you can import as needed. Children can implement many of their ideas when creating applications in Python by simply adding the necessary libraries. This approach increases the accessibility of Python. Children can code any program in Python in fewer steps than if they had to write in Java or C. Python is a very child-friendly programming language. They can experiment with different pieces of code and gradually assemble them into more meaningful programs to create their own video games and animations. It is clear that the Python programming language will be with us for a long time. Therefore, it is quite important for children to learn Python due to its wide range of applications. Knowledge of Python will also give them an edge when pursuing higher education in data science, automation, machine learning, and web development. Despite various improvements, the basic structure of the Python language remains unchanged. Therefore, learning Python programming for kids is a big plus, as their skills will definitely not become obsolete in the future. Learning Python will also increase children's ability for critical thinking. Yes, consistent reasoning is the key to understanding basic programming concepts. Therefore, writing Python code for various applications will allow children to visualize and ultimately comprehend complex abstract concepts of programming. This, in turn, will also improve their ability to analyze and solve mathematical problems. As a result, it can be noted that not only is there no need to abandon the idea of studying high-level programming languages in school, but on the contrary, learning Python, with the right approach and taking into account methodological features, will open up new horizons and opportunities for the student, since modern programming languages, improving, are becoming more versatile, flexible and simple, easy to understand and debug. This approach to learning high-level languages will allow you to train beginner programmers with diverse experience already at the school level in writing programs.

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